

Efficient Augmented Kalman Filter Parameter Tuning for Thermal Virtual Sensing in Electronic Systems

Matteo Depaola

Imec,
Siemens Industry Software NV,
KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium
matteo.depaola@imec.be

Daniel De Gregoriis

Siemens Industry Software NV
Leuven, Belgium
daniel.de_gregoriis@siemens.com

Robin Bornoff

Siemens Industry Software
Newbury, UK
robin.bornoff@siemens.com

Bart Vandevelde

Imec
Leuven, Belgium
bart.vandevelde@imec.be

David Moens

Flanders Make @ KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium
david.moens@kuleuven.be

Abstract—Digital Twins (DT) enable Thermal Virtual Sensing in electronics, to support e.g. thermal management strategies. A physics-based DT may consist of an Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF) employing a thermal Reduced Order Model. The AKF estimation performance depends on the tuning of the process noise covariance matrix. Many strategies, such as the L-curve method, have been introduced to address the problem of tuning. However, these approaches typically are time consuming, scaling along with the model size, and rely on expertise to be correctly used and interpreted. In this work, a new method is presented to tackle the tuning more time-efficiently and without requiring a-priori expertise. The proposed method is tested on the thermal model of a printed circuit board assembly (PCBA) system with multiple unknown Quantities of Interest. Results indicate similar estimation performance when compared to alternative tuning methods, whilst achieving a speed-up with factors ranging from 59 to 5000 to perform the tuning itself. This approach enables a time-efficient and expertise-free tuning of AKF, paving the way for a broader and faster industrial adoption of DTs.

Index Terms—digital twins, augmented kalman filter, thermal reduced order model, efficient tuning, electronics

I. INTRODUCTION

Physics-based Digital Twins (DTs) can be used with electronic systems [1] enabling Thermal Virtual Sensing (TVS) to support thermal management and health monitoring. DT frameworks can be represented by the Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF), extension of the Kalman Filter [2], often used in estimation problems for its optimal estimation properties and limited computational complexity. The AKF approach

The authors would like to thank the support from the European Commission through the Marie Curie project MIRELAI, funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No. 101072491). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Partners from the UK are supported by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council.

enables the estimation of unknown Quantities of Interest (QoIs), i.e. system inputs and parameters, which are otherwise unmeasurable in operation. It consists of a prediction step, i.e. a forward simulation step, followed by a correction step where physical measurement data is used to correct the numerical prediction.

The estimation performance of the AKF depends on sensor placement, measurement noise, and process noise covariance, i.e. model uncertainty. The location of sensors affects the estimate uncertainty, hence Optimal Sensor Placement strategies have been proposed to select informative and reliable sensor locations [1], [3]. Measurement noise, which degrades the estimate quality, is modelled as white Gaussian noise with its covariance usually extracted from measurement data. As discussed in [4], the estimation performance is ultimately governed by the ratio between the measurement noise and process noise covariance matrices, of which the tuning is an active research topic.

The process noise covariance matrix for the AKF is usually tuned considering a diagonal stencil for the sub-matrix corresponding to the unknown QoIs. Other than empirical tuning, rules of thumb have been proposed [5], [6], exploiting a-priori tuning experience for similar systems, which allows to set the process noise covariance matrix to achieve the desired performance. The L-curve tuning method [7] can be used, expanding the concept of empirical tuning to a more systematic exploration of the tuning space. Alternatively, optimization problems observing metrics like the *Normalized Innovation Squared* (NIS) and/or the *Normalized Estimation Error Squared* (NEES) [8], [9] have been proposed. All these methods can be computationally expensive, typically scaling at least proportionally with the system size, and require experience in tuning the AKF to be correctly used and interpreted.

In this work, a time-efficient methodology to tune the

process noise covariance matrix of the AKF is introduced that also reduces the threshold of necessary experience in tuning the AKF. The proposed method is based on the observation of two key performance indicators of the filter at steady-state, in its discrete-time formulation, describing the estimation responsiveness and the amount of noise in the estimate.

The proposed tuning methodology has been investigated on the thermal model of a PCBA system and compared with the L-curve method for achieved estimation performance and required time to tune the filter.

Finally, the time-efficiency of the proposed approach and future research steps are discussed.

II. FRAMEWORK

A. The parametric Reduced Order Model

The model employed in the DT is generated through Siemens Simcenter Flotherm [10], a simulation software for thermal analysis of electronic systems capable of exporting a Boundary Conditions Independent Reduced Order Model (BCI-ROM) [11], [12], allowing for real-time execution and preserving the dependency on the parameters of the boundary conditions, i.e. ambient temperature and Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC). The BCI-ROM is a first-order system defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{T}_r &= f(T_r, S, p) \\ &= M_r^{-1} (-K_r(p)T_r + V_u S + S_r^a(p)), \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

$$T = g(T_r) = V_o^T T_r, \quad (1b)$$

with input vector $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ containing the power dissipation, parameter vector $p \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$, temperature reduced state $T_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, and temperature field $T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_o}$. The reduced ambient source vector S_r^a models the heat exchange by thermal convection at the boundaries of the system. The matrices M_r and K_r represent the reduced thermal capacitance and the reduced thermal resistance. The matrices V_u and V_o^T respectively project the inputs onto the reduced space and the temperature reduced state onto the temperature field, and depend on the locations of inputs and sensors in the model.

Consistent with the AKF formulation, the following state-space formulation can be adopted for (1):

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u, p) = A(p)x + Bu + d(p), \quad (2a)$$

$$y = Cx. \quad (2b)$$

B. The Augmented Kalman Filter

The estimation of unknown QoIs, i.e. system inputs u and parameters p , is enabled by including them in the augmented state x_a as

$$x_a = \begin{bmatrix} x^\top & u^\top & p^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top = \begin{bmatrix} x^\top & q^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top. \quad (3)$$

Since no prior information about the augmented state variables q is available, their dynamics are modelled by implementing

a zeroth-order random-walk scheme in the system equations and by including process noises so that

$$\dot{x} = f_a(x_a) + w_a, \quad (4a)$$

$$y = C_a x_a + \nu, \quad (4b)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} f_a(x_a) &= \begin{bmatrix} f(x_a)^\top & 0_{1 \times n_q} \end{bmatrix}^\top, \quad w_a = \begin{bmatrix} w_x^\top & w_q^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top, \\ \begin{bmatrix} w_x \\ w_q \end{bmatrix} &\sim \mathbb{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0_{n_x \times 1} \\ 0_{n_q \times 1} \end{bmatrix}, Q_a = \begin{bmatrix} Q_x & 0_{n_x \times n_q} \\ 0_{n_q \times n_x} & Q_q \end{bmatrix} \right), \\ C_a &= \begin{bmatrix} C & 0_{n_o \times n_q} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \nu \sim \mathbb{N}(0, R). \end{aligned}$$

The estimation performance of the filter depends on the matrices Q_a and R . Assuming the used sensors are affected by similar noise, $R = \sigma_v^2 \times I_{n_o}$, with the variance σ_v^2 obtained from the sensor data sheet or by observing the noise in the measurement data. Usually, in the context of AKF, Q_x is a zero matrix while Q_q is a diagonal matrix, of which the terms are to be tuned following a tuning strategy, subject of this work.

The filter is defined at the k -th iteration with the equations:

$$\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^- = f_{a,d}(\hat{x}_{a,k}^+), \quad (5a)$$

$$P_{a,k+1}^- = A_{a,d}(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-) P_{a,k}^+ A_{a,d}^\top(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-) + Q_{a,d}, \quad (5b)$$

$$K_{a,k+1} = P_{a,k+1}^- C_a^\top \left(C_a P_{a,k+1}^- C_a^\top + R \right)^{-1}, \quad (5c)$$

$$\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^+ = \hat{x}_{a,k+1}^- + K_{a,k+1} \left(\tilde{y} - C_a \hat{x}_{a,k+1}^- \right), \quad (5d)$$

$$P_{a,k+1}^+ = (I - K_{a,k+1} C_a) P_{a,k+1}^-, \quad (5e)$$

where (5a) and (5b) define the prediction step, to calculate an a-priori state estimate $(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-, P_{a,k+1}^-)$, and (5c), (5d), and (5e) define the correction step, to calculate an a-posteriori state estimate $(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^+, P_{a,k+1}^+)$. Discretization is executed, with a selected sampling time t_s , to obtain $f_{a,d}$, $A_{a,d}$ (by linearizing $f_{a,d}$ in $\hat{x}_{a,k}^+$) and $Q_{a,d}$ [13]. The filter is initialized by setting the initial condition $(\hat{x}_{a,0}^+, P_{a,0}^+)$.

III. COST FUNCTIONS FOR EFFICIENT TUNING

A method is introduced to tune the covariance terms on the main diagonal of $Q_{q,d}$ based on two estimation performance key indicators by analysing the AKF in its steady-state discrete-time formulation.

The steady-state augmented state estimate covariance matrix is computed by solving the discrete-time Algebraic Riccati Equation:

$$P_{a,d} = F_a P_{a,d} F_a^\top + Q_{a,d} - F_a K_{a,d} (C_a P_{a,d} F_a^\top), \quad (6)$$

where $F_a = A_{a,d}(\hat{x}_{a,ss})$ is the state transition matrix of the AKF at steady-state $\hat{x}_{a,ss}$, and $K_{a,d}$ is the Kalman gain at

steady-state obtained using $P_{a,d}$ in place of $P_{a,k+1}^-$ in (5c). Since the AKF estimate will tend to the reference:

$$\hat{x}_{a,ss} = x_{a,ss} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ss}^\top(q_n) & q_n^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top, \quad (7)$$

with q_n the indicated nominal values for the QoIs.

The state-space AKF equations from the measurements \tilde{y} to the estimated QoIs \hat{q} are:

$$\hat{x}_{a,k+1} = (F_a - K_{a,d}C_aF_a)\hat{x}_{a,k} + K_{a,d}\tilde{y}_k, \quad (8a)$$

$$\hat{q}_k = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{n_q \times n_x} & I_{n_q} \end{bmatrix} \hat{x}_{a,k}. \quad (8b)$$

Moving from the state-space formulation to the transfer function formulation:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{q} &= T_{\hat{q},y}(f)\tilde{y} = T_{\hat{q},y}(f)(y + \nu) = \\ &T_{\hat{q},y}(f)T_{y,q}(f)q + T_{\hat{q},y}(f)\nu = \\ &T_{\hat{q},q}(f)q + T_{\hat{q},y}(f)\nu = \hat{q}_s + \nu_{\hat{q}}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $T_{A,B}(f)$ indicates a transfer function from B to A , and \hat{q}_s and $\nu_{\hat{q}}$ are respectively the signal and noise components of \hat{q} . A well performing AKF computes an estimate \hat{q} that tracks the reference signal q and contains a limited amount of noise $\nu_{\hat{q}}$. An optimization problem can be defined to solve for the covariance terms in $Q_{q,d}$ to minimize cost functions regarding the two requirements.

For the first requirement, the closed-loop transfer function $T_{\hat{q},q}(f)$, which works as a low-pass filter [14], should be defined such that it has a large enough bandwidth, coinciding with the cut-off frequency f_c , that is the frequency at which the transfer function's magnitude equals $-3dB$. By requiring the AKF closed-loop transfer function's cut-off frequency to be equal to a previously indicated input parameter of target cut-off frequency $f_{c,i}$, a *target cut-off frequency cost function* c_{TF} is defined as:

$$c_{TF} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_q} (\log(f_c(T_{\hat{q},q_i})) - \log(f_{c,i}))^2. \quad (10)$$

For the second requirement, the variance of the noise component $\nu_{\hat{q}}$ should be limited by observing its noise power [15], that is the sum of all the noise power contributions from the used measurements to a QoI estimate. By requiring the standard deviation of the noise component $\nu_{\hat{q}}$ to be equal to a previously indicated input parameter of noise bound standard deviation b_i , a *bounded noise cost function* c_{BN} is defined as:

$$c_{BN} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_q} \left(\log \left(\sqrt{\sum_{o=1}^{N_o} P_{\nu_{\hat{q}_i, y_o}}} \right) - \log \left(\frac{b_i}{3} \right) \right)^2, \quad (11a)$$

$$P_{\nu_{\hat{q}_i, y_o}} = N_{\nu_o} \int_0^{f_b} |T_{\hat{q}_i, y_o}(f)|^2 df, \quad (11b)$$

where b_i is divided by 3 to make sure $\nu_{\hat{q}}$ is contained in the bound with a probability of 99.7%, the bandwidth $f_b = f_s/2$ according to the Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem, with f_s

Fig. 1: Top view of the test PCBA. Chips are enumerated from 1 to 6. The red square indicates the location of a sensor BS on top of the board.

the sampling frequency, and $N_{\nu_o} = \sigma_{\nu_o}^2/f_b^1$ is the noise power spectral density of sensor o (constant under white noise assumption), with $\sigma_{\nu_o}^2$ the variance of the measurement noise of sensor o .

The key performance indicators in c_{TF} and c_{BN} are found to depend quasi linearly on the process noise covariance terms and, therefore, the cost functions appear to be convex. A logarithmic scale is used for the covariance terms and the elements in (10) and (11) to conveniently explore both domain and codomain as well as achieve a time-efficient tuning performance.

IV. RESULTS

The considered setup consists of a $60mm \times 67mm \times 1.56mm$ test PCBA shown from the top in Fig. 1. The board, made out of FR4, features 6 silicon chips, several interface components, and a copper circuitry on the top. Chip 1 is of size $6.4mm \times 6.4mm \times 0.4mm$ and chips 2-6 are of size $3.2mm \times 3.2mm \times 0.4mm$. They are glued to the board through a $40\mu m$ thick die-attach. The circuitry is $17.6\mu m$ thick and is discretized in the software with thermal parameter values calculated based on the percentage of copper and FR4 in the corresponding local volume region. Located underneath chips 2 and 3 are thermal vias with a 2×2 grid, $1mm$ pitch, and holes with $0.2mm$ diameter, modelled as blocks of material TV. The thermal parameter values are in Table I. Temperature measurement data come from the 6 chips and from an additional sensor BS on top of the board.

The HTC on top and on the lateral system boundaries is set at $10W/m^2K$ to model natural air convection. The HTC at the bottom system boundary ($bHTC$) switches every 300s between $470W/m^2K$ and $122W/m^2K$, to model a dry attach

¹One-sided power spectral density is considered

TABLE I: Thermal parameter values of the materials used in the model.

Material	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]		Density [kg/m ³]	Specific heat [J/kgK]
	In-plane	Normal		
FR4	0.8	0.38	1850	1100
Silicon	120		2330	700
Glue	0.3		2000	1000
Copper	385		8930	385
TV	0.37	15.0	1436.3	762.5

to an (unmodelled) aluminium cold plate depending on the air-gap thickness, an uncertain parameter usually in the range [50 μ m, 200 μ m]. Power dissipation ($U\#$) switches every 150s in between 0.1W and 0.8W for chip 1 and in between 0.1W and 0.3W for chips 2-6. The reference q_r includes the power dissipation $U1 - 6$ and $bHTC$, that is:

$$q_{r,k} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{1,k} & u_{2,k} & u_{3,k} & u_{4,k} & u_{5,k} & u_{6,k} & p_k \end{bmatrix}^\top. \quad (12)$$

The nominal values q_n are set to 250W/m²K for bHTC, 0.4W for chip 1, and 0.2W for chips 2-6.

The system is at ambient temperature (293.15K) at $t = 0s$. White Gaussian noise with a variance of $\sigma_\nu^2 = 0.25K^2$ is added to the outputs to generate measurement data.

The AKF requires the setting of $\hat{x}_{a,0}$, $P_{a,0}$, $Q_{a,d}$, R , and t_s . Since the system is known to be at ambient temperature at $t = 0s$, \hat{x}_0 represents this condition and $P_{x,0} = 0_{n_x \times n_x}$. No previous knowledge about q is provided. We choose to set $\hat{u}_0 = 0_{n_u \times 1}$, $\hat{p}_0 = 250W/m^2K$, $P_{u,0} = 1W^2 \times I_{n_u}$ and $P_{p,0} = 2.5 \times 10^5 W^2 / (m^4 K^2)$. The setting of $Q_{q,d}$ in $Q_{a,d}$ is investigated in the following while $R = \sigma_\nu^2 \cdot I_{n_o}$. The sampling time $t_s = 0.01s$.

For a computational overview, the simulations analysed in this work were carried out on a laptop featuring a CPU Intel i9-13900H in Matlab [16], the ROM size was with $n_x = 95$ state variables, and an implicit Euler integrator scheme was used to simulate the model. Constrained optimization problems were solved using *fmincon* from the optimization toolbox with interior-point algorithm, a step tolerance of $1e-10$, a function tolerance of $1e-6$, initial guesses of $1e-10$ and bounds [1e-16, 1e+16] for all covariance terms.

A. L-curve tuning method

The L-curve method [7] consists of observing the trend of an error indicator, e.g. the Mean Residual Norm $MRN = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{N_k} (||\hat{y}(k) - \tilde{y}(k)||) \right) / N_k$, and a smoothing indicator, e.g. the trace of P at the last iteration of the AKF, for increasing values of a process noise covariance parameter corresponding to the observed QoI, given (optionally simulated)

Fig. 2: L-curve for U1-6. Two bending regions are identified around $\sigma_u^2 = 1e-7$ and $\sigma_u^2 = 1e4$. The first indicates an optimal solution for inputs estimation, whilst the second indicates measurement noise integration.

measurement data. The curve will sharply decrease in MRN at first until a bending region where a small decrease of MRN translates into a large increase of trace of P . The interpretation of such behavior is that most of relevant information from measurement data has been integrated already and a further increase of the tuning parameter would bring to increasing measurement noise integration for the most. To visualize the L-curve, a $\log - \log$ plot is usually adopted with MRN on the x-axis and trace of P on the y-axis.

The L-curve in Fig. 2 was generated simulating the AKF while considering the inputs u_{1-6} as unknown QoIs and the parameter p to be known. To simplify the problem, the process noise variances corresponding to the 6 inputs were assumed to be equal ($\sigma_u^2 = \sigma_{u,1-6}^2$), exploiting their similarity. 41 values on a logarithmic scale were tested for σ_u^2 in the range [1e-10, 1e+10]. Simulating all conditions took 5000s. A first bending in Fig. 2 occurs around the selected optimal value $\sigma_u^2 = 1e-7$. A second bending occurring around $\sigma_u^2 = 1e4$ indicates that the estimated output started to follow the measurement, including the measurement noise.

Similarly, the curve in Fig. 3 was generated simulating the AKF while considering the parameter p as an unknown QoI and the system inputs u_{1-6} to be known. Again, 41 values on a logarithmic scale were tested for σ_p^2 in the range [1e-10, 1e+10]. Simulating all conditions took almost 10000s, due to the introduced non-linearity of the system when considering a varying parameter, which led to iterative state matrix computation, and consequent increased computational burden. A bending occurs around the selected optimal value of $\sigma_p^2 = 1e-2$. Unlike the previous study, there is no sign of bending indicating measurement noise integration. Instead, the curve shows an unstable behavior from $\sigma_p^2 = 1e4$, indicating occurrence of unstable estimation dynamics, due to the non-

Fig. 3: L-curve for bHTC. A bending region is identified around $\sigma_p^2 = 1e-2$ indicating an optimal solution for parameter estimation. After $\sigma_p^2 = 1e4$ the curve indicates unstable estimation dynamics.

TABLE II: Tuning results for target cut-off frequency of $0.2Hz$

QoIs	U1-6	bHTC	U1-6&bHTC
$\sigma_{u_1}^2$	$2.37e-7$	-	$3.75e-7$
$\sigma_{u_2}^2$	$2.18e-8$	-	$1.25e-6$
$\sigma_{u_3}^2$	$2.40e-8$	-	$1.38e-6$
$\sigma_{u_4}^2$	$1.72e-8$	-	$5.48e-8$
$\sigma_{u_5}^2$	$1.49e-8$	-	$3.81e-8$
$\sigma_{u_6}^2$	$1.56e-8$	-	$3.38e-8$
σ_p^2	-	2.9255	247.7
Time	32s	2s	193s

linearity.

B. Proposed tuning method - target cut-off frequency

The closed loop transfer functions of the AKF $T_{\hat{q}_i, q_i}$ behave like low-pass filters [14]. After defining a frequency up to which no loss is desired, the cut-off frequency can be set to be larger by e.g. a safety factor of 2 or 3 at least. For the investigated system, after previous analysis, no loss was desired up to $0.05Hz$ and a safety factor of 4 was chosen, eventually indicating a target cut-off frequency of $0.2Hz$ for all QoIs.

Covariance terms obtained using the proposed method are shown in Table II, reporting separated tuning (U1-6 or bHTC) and combined tuning (U1-6&bHTC), and the optimization problems reached a cost function value smaller than $1e-10$, indicating optimal solutions. Tuning the covariances for the

Fig. 4: Estimation performance comparison in between AKF with parameters tuned with L-curve or with target cut-off frequency of $0.2Hz$ with separated or combined tuning.

unknown inputs took 32s compared to the 5000s when using the L-curve method, for a reduction factor of 156. Tuning the covariances for the unknown parameter took 2s compared to the 10000s when using the L-curve method, for a reduction factor of 5000. Tuning the covariances for all unknown QoIs concurrently took 193s which can be compared to the total time required to evaluate the 2 L-curves of 15000s, for a reduction factor of 77.

Covariance values corresponding to the unknown inputs are close to those obtained with the L-curve, differing for a factor of 13.8 at most, in particular for U2-3 where higher values were required due to the presence of thermal vias, which make estimation more challenging [17]. The covariance terms corresponding to the unknown parameter differ for 2 and 4 orders of magnitude, respectively for the separated and combined tuning. The effects are evident in the estimation comparison in Fig. 4 where the bHTC estimate using covariance terms obtained with combined tuning shows a noise component with power $P_{\nu_{\hat{a}_p}} = 2750W^2/m^4K^2$, indicating that a cut-off frequency of $0.2Hz$ for this QoI leads to excessive measurement noise integration. However, the bHTC estimate using covariance terms obtained with separated tuning shows a noise component with power $P_{\nu_{\hat{a}_p}} = 76W^2/m^4K^2$ (36 times smaller), indicating that the actual cut-off frequency

Fig. 5: Bode magnitude diagram of $T_{\hat{p},p}$ in the case of separated tuning (blue line) and combined tuning (green line). Although having the same target cut-off frequency requirement, the cut-off frequency corresponding to covariance terms from separate tuning changes when considering the whole estimation problem, that is including the unknown inputs.

is less than $0.2Hz$, although the same value was set as requirement.

To further highlight this effect, notice that if the covariance terms obtained with separated tuning optimization are used in the cost function for the combined tuning, the cost function value is 0.2191. This indicates that the solution obtained with separated tuning leads to different cut-off frequencies when the whole tuning problem is considered. Therefore, although such a tuning can be executed separately to achieve cut-off frequencies close to the requirement, estimation performance could eventually differ, as shown in Fig. 5. Solving a combined tuning optimization problem is therefore recommended.

C. Proposed tuning method - bounded noise

The noise bounds in (11) are expressed in absolute scales. To simplify and generalize the setting of the requirement, noise bounds have been assigned to be 2% of nominal values q_n , resulting in $\pm 5W/m^2K$ for *bHTC*, $\pm 0.008W$ for *U1*, and $\pm 0.004W$ for *U2 - 6*.

Covariance terms obtained using the proposed method are shown in Table III, reporting separated tuning (U1-6 or bHTC) and combined tuning (U1-6&bHTC), and the optimization problems reached a cost function value smaller than $1e - 10$, indicating optimal solutions. Tuning the covariances for the unknown inputs took 87s compared to the 5000s when using the L-curve method, for a reduction factor of 59. Tuning the covariances for the unknown parameter took 15s compared to the 10000s when using the L-curve method, for a reduction factor of 667. Tuning the covariances for all unknown QoIs concurrently took 172s which can be compared to the total time required to evaluate the 2 L-curves of 15000s, for a reduction factor of 87.

TABLE III: Tuning results for bounded noise to 2%

QoIs	U1-6	bHTC	U1-6&bHTC
$\sigma_{u_1}^2$	$2.38e - 7$	-	$2.33e - 7$
$\sigma_{u_2}^2$	$9.19e - 8$	-	$8.61e - 8$
$\sigma_{u_3}^2$	$8.73e - 8$	-	$8.12e - 8$
$\sigma_{u_4}^2$	$1.00e - 7$	-	$9.84e - 8$
$\sigma_{u_5}^2$	$1.08e - 7$	-	$1.06e - 7$
$\sigma_{u_6}^2$	$1.06e - 7$	-	$1.04e - 7$
σ_p^2	-	0.0364	0.0250
Time	87s	15s	172s

All covariance values are close to those obtained with the L-curve. The estimation performance reported in Fig. 6 are indeed comparable. To further highlight this similarity, notice that if the covariance terms obtained by separated tuning are used in the cost function for the combined tuning, the resulting value is 0.0032. This indicates that the solution obtained with separated tuning leads to similar noise bounds when the whole tuning problem is considered. In this case, a separated tuning can be preferred over a combined tuning to further speed up solving for the covariance terms, resulting in a total tuning time of 102s instead of 172s.

V. DISCUSSION

While achieving AKF performance comparable to the state-of-the-art tuning methods such as the L-curve method, the proposed tuning method allows for a more efficient exploration of the tuning space, as well as using objective performance requirements such as cut-off frequency and bounded noise to define an optimal overall tuning solution. To further speed-up tuning the AKF, the optimality tolerances could be adjusted to reduce required tuning accuracy whilst not impacting the overall estimation performance but allowing to relax solving of the optimization problem. Additionally, adopting a similar stencil for multiple unknown QoIs, as in e.g. the L-curve tuning method, could further reduce the overall optimization problem complexity.

The optimization problems presented in this work seem to converge to global optima, but no proof of convexity was given and the presence of local minima should be investigated. Also, sensor placement notoriously impacts the AKF estimation performance [1] and the effect of different sensing locations on tuning must be addressed. In addition, although in this work only optimization problems using one kind of cost function were explored, the tuning could be carried out by weighing the two requirements for each QoI. Furthermore, the concepts of the proposed cost functions can be exploited to define non-linear constraints to ensure the AKF closed-loop transfer function's cut-off frequency and the noise component of an estimated QoI are respectively lower and upper bounded.

Fig. 6: Estimation performance comparison in between AKF with parameters tuned with L-curve or with bounded noise of 2% with separated or combined tuning.

The alternative methods for tuning the AKF require experience in setting the problem (generation of measurement data, setting of weights, definition of tuning space) and interpreting the results, and are not time-efficient. The L-curve method typically only allows to tune one covariance term at a time, and cannot therefore deal with tuning all the covariance values of interest at once, resulting in an estimation performance change, as reported in section IV-B, when multiple unknown QoIs are to be estimated. Optimization problems for NIS and NEES metrics usually require even more tuning time than the L-curve method, especially considering the well-known risk of local minima for which e.g. a genetic algorithm must be employed [8].

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach has been tested on the thermal model of a PCBA system and compared with the L-curve tuning method, highlighting a reduction factor in tuning ranging from 59 to 5000. Similar estimation performance has been achieved, especially when using optimal covariance terms from the optimization using the bounded noise cost function.

Future studies will further explore tuning problem simplifications, weighing of the proposed requirements, presence

of local minima, dependence on sensor configurations, and requirement based non-linear constraints.

REFERENCES

- [1] Matteo Depaola, Daniel De Gregoriis, Robin Bornoff, Bart Vandeveld, and David Moens. Optimal sensor placement for thermal virtual sensing in electronic systems using augmented kalman filtering. In *2025 31st International Workshop on Thermal Investigations of ICs and Systems (THERMINIC)*, pages 1–6, 2025.
- [2] Rudolph Emil Kalman. A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems. *Trans. ASME-J. Basic Eng.*, 82(1):35–45, 1960.
- [3] Roberta Cumbo, Lorenzo Mazzanti, Tommaso Tamarozzi, Pavel Jiranek, Wim Desmet, and Frank Naets. Advanced optimal sensor placement for kalman-based multiple-input estimation. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 160:107830, 2021.
- [4] Simone Formentin and Sergio Bittanti. An insight into noise covariance estimation for kalman filter design. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 47:2358–2363, 2014.
- [5] Cristian Enrico Capalbo, Daniel De Gregoriis, Tommaso Tamarozzi, Hendrik Devriendt, Frank Naets, Giuseppe Carbone, and Domenico Mundo. Parameter, input and state estimation for linear structural dynamics using parametric model order reduction and augmented kalman filtering. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 185:109799, 2023.
- [6] Roberta Cumbo, Tommaso Tamarozzi, Karl Janssens, and Wim Desmet. Kalman-based load identification and full-field estimation analysis on industrial test case. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 2019.
- [7] Silvia Vettori, Emilio Di Lorenzo, Bart Peeters, Marcin M. Luczak, and Eleni Chatzi. An adaptive-noise augmented kalman filter approach for input-state estimation in structural dynamics. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 184:109654, 2023.
- [8] Michael Theiler, Dominik Schneider, and Christian Endisch. Kalman filter tuning using multi-objective genetic algorithm for state and parameter estimation of lithium-ion cells. *Batteries*, 8(9), 2022.
- [9] Zhaozhong Chen, Harel Biggie, Nisar Ahmed, Simon Julier, and Christoffer Heckman. Kalman filter auto-tuning with consistent and robust bayesian optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 60(2):2236–2250, 2024.
- [10] Siemens Digital Industries Software. Simcenter flotherm.
- [11] Lorenzo Codecasa, Vincenzo d’Alessandro, Alessandro Magnani, and Niccolò Rinaldi. Matrix reduction tool for creating boundary condition independent dynamic compact thermal models. In *2015 21st International Workshop on Thermal Investigations of ICs and Systems (THERMINIC)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2015.
- [12] Lorenzo Codecasa, Vincenzo d’Alessandro, Alessandro Magnani, Niccolò Rinaldi, and Peter J. Zampardi. Fast novel thermal analysis simulation tool for integrated circuits (fantastic). In *20th International Workshop on Thermal Investigations of ICs and Systems*, pages 1–6, 2014.
- [13] Dan Simon. *Optimal state estimation: Kalman, H infinity, and nonlinear approaches*. John Wiley & Sons, 2006.
- [14] Bart Forrier, Mahmoud Elkafafy, Alberto Garcia de Miguel, Mariano Alvarez Blanco, and Karl Janssens. Automated tuning of kalman based virtual sensors for full-field acoustic pressure. pages 12–15, 2022.
- [15] Alan V. Oppenheim and George C. Verghese. *Signals, Systems & Inference*. Prentice-Hall signal processing series. Pearson, 2016.
- [16] The MathWorks Inc. Matlab.
- [17] Matteo Depaola, Daniel De Gregoriis, Gwendal Jouan, Robin Bornoff, Bart Vandeveld, and David Moens. Thermal virtual sensing for electronic components and system: exploring the robustness of kalman filtering. *Proceedings of ISMA/USD 2024*, 2024.